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Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17022260

Infrastructure resilience forecasting: A holistic resilience assessment framework

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Abstract:

In view of the increased frequency and intensity of climate change-induced infrastructure failures there is an urgent need to adapt infrastructure to ensure continuous and reliable service provision. The UK's vulnerability to climate change is becoming increasingly evident as the replacement and upgrading of economic infrastructure are progressing with a considerably slower pace. Hence, a holistic resilience assessment framework, that addresses the vulnerabilities of infrastructure to the hazards of climate exacerbated shocks and informs adaptation planning, is needed.

Inviting feedback from the conference, this paper investigates the challenges involved in establishing a place-based holistic resilience assessment framework, exploring the scope of infrastructure to be included, the need for a benchmark reference point, the indicators and metrics to be utilised, and outcome-driven forecasting output. The paper outlines the development and high-level exploratory testing of a novel framework designed to avoid abstraction and enable place-based resilience forecasting that will inform adaptation processes whilst preventing infrastructure overcapitalisation, resource overconsumption, or maladaptation

Keywords: #resilience #townplanning #climatechange #adaptation

Main highlights:

- Climate change is exposing weak points in the UK's infrastructure systems through more frequent droughts, intense storms, sea level rise, higher temperatures, and heavier rainfall.

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- A gap in the literature is identified whereby resilience is discussed without a clear baseline for normal service or any measurement of the buffer needed to protect systems from climate stresses.
- A draft place-based holistic Resilience Assessment Framework is proposed and tested at high level.
- Feedback from the conference on the draft Resilience Assessment Framework described here is sought as the study moves from conceptual stage to practically applicable tool.

Abbreviations

BGS	The British Geological Survey
CCC	Climate Change Committee
CCRA	Climate Change Risk Assessment
CIRIA	Construction Industry Research and Information Association
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
DNO	Distribution Network Operators
EA	Environment Agency
FC	Forestry Commission
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GEMA	The Gas and Electricity Markets Authority
HA	Highways Authority
HSE	Health and Safety Executive
IDB	Internal Drainage Board
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LA	Local Authority
LABC	Local Authority Building Control
LLFA	Lead Local Flood Authority
NE	Natural England
NHS	National Health Service
NIC	National Infrastructure Commission
NCSC	National Cyber Security Centre
NFU	National Farmers Union
NR	Network Rail
OFGEM	Office of Gas and Electricity Markets
OFWAT	The Water Services Regulation Authority
ORR	Office for road and rail
PESA	Public Expenditure Statistical Analyses
PTAL	Public Transport Accessibility Levels
RAF	Resilience Assessment Framework
RMA	Risk Management Authority
SSEN	Scottish and southern electricity networks
UKHSA	UK Health Security Agency

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Introduction

Climate change is exposing weak points in the UK's infrastructure systems through more frequent droughts, intense storms, sea level rise, higher temperatures, and heavier rainfall (Cunliffe-Hall, 2024). These hazards are amplifying vulnerabilities and increasing the likelihood and severity of infrastructure failures (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2021). As global temperatures rise by 3.1°C, above preindustrial levels by 2100 (Olhoff et al., 2024), infrastructure resilience must be strengthened to ensure continuity of services (Climate Change Committee, 2022, Labuschagne et al., 2022).

The UK Government has failed to meet its commitment to set national resilience standards by 2025 (Freng et al., 2023), in line with calls from the NIC (2024) and priorities outlined in the National Resilience Strategy (HM Government, 2022a). National policy led mitigation and adaptation efforts have been insufficient to counteract the country's increasing climate risks (Joint Committee on the National Security Strategy, 2023; National Infrastructure Commission, 2021).

A gap in the resilience assessment of climate driven risks to infrastructure exists (Wilson B, 2023. Public Accounts Committee, 2024) with only a limited palette of forecasting tools available (Medland et al., 2024) and many, even well utilised government flood risk data, for example, not designed for use at a granular scale (Environment Agency, 2024). A comprehensive framework that anticipates future shocks, integrates adaptation, and enables resilience measures to be valued prior to disruptive events is needed (HM Government, 2022a) (Dianat et al., 2022).

Inviting feedback from the conference, via questions, expert informant interviews and correspondence, this paper aims to respond to the gap in the literature by setting out the challenges around the development of a Resilience Assessment Framework (RAF) designed to evaluate infrastructure vulnerability holistically across scales, from the perspective of place. Central to this research is the acknowledgment of infrastructure interdependencies across scales (Cloete, 2017), recognition of the entanglement of socio-ecological and socio-technical infrastructure systems with complexities surrounding finance, ownership, and agency (Berrouet et al., 2018) and how these effect communities and households.

Methodology

The research took an inductive approach guided by a qualitative research paradigm and is structured around four components:

- (1) Conducting a literature review (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005) (Munn et al., 2018), to identify the need for a place-based cross-scale holistic RAF and clarifying key concepts.
- (2) The architecture of the experimental RAF and indicator selection was established.

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(3) Undertaking initial high level desktop exploratory test case applications of the framework (Prasad Bhatta, 2018) to examine outcomes and the explore the repeatability and efficiency of the process.

(4) Synthesising results and findings through discussion and the conclusions.

Definitions, Concepts and Framing

What is Infrastructure and how is it categorised?

Infrastructure enables the management and transportation of resources or services to reach places that require them (Fulmer, 2009). Infrastructure is an interconnected system of systems and assets that, when operating optimally, enable the efficient and sustainable use of resources (Cloete, 2017). Infrastructure can be categorised through taxonomy or through characterisation i.e., one set of definitions describe what infrastructure is and the other observes what infrastructure does (Fulmer, 2009) (Buhr, 2003).

Which elements of infrastructure are considered here?

This study sets out a holistic framing of infrastructure and considers all components and systems that provide or enable the provision of services that ‘sustain, or enhance societal living conditions’ (Fulmer, 2009) in contemporary Britain from the perspective of place. The focus here is infrastructure critical to supporting the determinants of wellbeing (Dasgupta & Weale, 1992). Economic, social, and environmental infrastructure is subdivided and described by a total of twenty categories as listed in Table 1, Example test case desktop scoping review: high level summary.

What is Resilience?

The literature demonstrates broad agreement that resilience functions as a buffer between normal operations and exceptional events—a latent capacity that enables systems to absorb shocks, maintain function, or, significantly and separate from robustness, recover to a stable state (Folke et al., 2010) (Pörtner et al., 2022) (Norris F & Stevens S, 2007). Similarly, Folke et al. (2002) and Luthar et al. (2000) describe resilience as the capacity to absorb and adapt to disruptions while maintaining core functions. Frameworks by Contas (2014) and Béné (2012) outline three components: the ex-ante state (pre-shock), disturbance (shock/stress), and ex-post state (post-shock outcomes) yet definitions fail to specify what constitutes “normal” service.

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How can Resilience be forecast?

Quantifying resilience, and lack of robustness, has challenges related to scale, weighting, temporality, and the degree of user agency (Linkov & Trump, 2019). Technical issues—such as infrastructure life cycle, degradation, and maintenance—further complicate assessment (Lauren, 2021). These constraints suggest that a single, aggregated, resilience metric may be neither feasible nor meaningful (Hallegatte & Engle, 2019). Probabilistic forecasting, using statistical models to estimate the likelihood that infrastructure systems will withstand or recover from climate-related hazards under varying future climate scenarios, enables the definition of a behavioural trajectory in the three ways listed below, all of which accept a period of disruption:

A - Robust behavior: the system returns to its initial state before the disruptive event (Bruneau M et al., 2003), absorbs the impacts of perturbations (Francis & Bekera, 2014) or even reaches an improved state compared to the initial state (Ayyub, 2014).

B - Ductile behavior: the system comes back to a certain level, but its functionality is not completely restored (Decò et al., 2013).

C - Collapsing behavior: the system cannot recover its functionality (Nan & Sansavini, 2017).

Which Climate Hazards and Infrastructure Vulnerabilities are considered?

Climate change is increasing the incidence and magnitude of five hazards: sea level rise, extreme heat, drought, extreme precipitation, and more frequent and violent storms (Met Office, 2022). However, factors influencing resilience are not confined to sudden events but also those related to maintenance practices, entropy and reliability determined by, amongst other things, the quality of component manufacture, construction and design standards (Graham S, 2009). Combining overlapping infrastructure vulnerabilities identified in the UK Climate Change Risk Assessment (Climate Change Committee, 2022), this study considers sixteen key risks (see Figures 1 and 2 and Table 1). Each infrastructure element and interconnected systems (Pescaroli & Alexander, 2018) across scales (Young & Hall, 2015) is assessed for exposure to these risks.

What does Infrastructure Failure look like?

Infrastructure failure has qualities of scale, consequence, and temporality (Kelly, 2015). The extent of harm resulting from such failure depends on whether it involves a single event, multiple simultaneous failures, or a cascading sequence of failures (Wang et al., 2012). Vulnerable infrastructure is likely to experience more frequent and prolonged service disruptions, with an increasing degree of impact on lives and livelihoods (Pant et. al, 2020), the extent of impact of disruption which can be described as minor, limited, moderate, significant, catastrophic (Cabinet Office, 2023). Economic loss associated with disruptions is determined not only by the affected component or service but also by the interruption of

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interdependent components or services and the economic activities they support (Kelly, 2015).

Indicator Selection

Table 2 below outlines the indicators and sources of information utilised for this initial desktop review of the framework methodology. All indicators have weaknesses, and only a few will be a precise measure of exactly what is needed (Hallegatte & Engle, 2019). For example, rather than measure access to nearby bus routes, train and tram services, and cycle lanes in a bespoke fashion for each site, the RAF will utilise the Public Transport Accessibility Level (PTAL) rating, using the data available from county councils. Performance related data from OFGEM and OFWAT is utilised, as is Local Authority statistics regarding waste collection, school closures, and socioeconomic factors. Data from Natural England (Natural England, 2023), Government departments information on quality of life (Ministry of Housing, 2019), and flood mapping (HM Government, 2025) are also useful risk screening tools.

Positionality and Value Based Judgements

As a construction industry professional the author, also a PhD researcher, recognises that this positionality has influenced the framing, indicator selection, and interpretation of the findings of this study. This positionality also informs the technical feasibility of adaptations, stakeholder priorities, and real-world implementation cross sector challenges of climate change resilience. The selection of the test case sites, the weight given to each climate change vulnerability, and the estimation of performance thresholds or tipping point involves value-based judgements to varying degrees that can only be partially inferred from empirical evidence (Buth et al., 2017). Fact-based approaches are used as far as practicable, and the study will be transparent as to where value-based judgements have been made and why, as referred to in Table 1 and Table 2.

Developing The Framework

Test Cases

Spanning over 770 square miles (nearly 2000 square kilometres) West Sussex has a population of around 900,000 concentrated in towns and coastal areas (West Sussex County Council, 2024). Over half the county lies within the South Downs National Park and Areas of Outstanding Natural Beauty where development is restricted. As a result, demand for new housing is largely being met through large developments on low lying areas near the coast. These areas face significant infrastructure strain from population growth (Hansard, 2020). The county's mix of geographic and planning constraints, topography, and housing demand makes it a valuable test area for this study. Ten test sites were selected across the county

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(refer to Table 3) to demonstrate a broad range of socioeconomic and environmental characteristics. The test cases vary in their locations, from rural, peri-urban and urban, and in lifecycle phase - i.e. older home that have been inhabited for decades are included along with new homes and developments at the planning stage. Addresses of the individual sites are anonymised and the site-specific data made nonattributable and will not be used or made available for any purposes other than the research project.

Establishing a place-based Ex-Ante Benchmark

As illustrated in Figure 1 below, an ex-ante benchmark is established to define normal service over a fixed period at the point of delivery. The benchmark enables comparison of climate change impacts on infrastructure performance across sites and the establishment of relative resilience standards. Place-based ex-ante assessments begin with an analysis of the site's topography, microclimate, and geographic characteristics, as well as its socioeconomic profile. Then one of three potential behavioural designations of resilience are assigned to each of the twenty identified infrastructure components across four defined scales of granularity, using data for the year 2021, the reference point corresponding to the most recent national census, providing socioeconomic data (Office for National Statistics, 2021)). The process utilises publicly available and verifiable indicators which are aligned with the 16 infrastructure vulnerabilities - the climate change vulnerabilities manifest when the resilience buffer, or threshold of an infrastructure system or element is exceeded (threshold exceedance). Each benchmark is context specific thus not all vulnerabilities will be relevant.

Generating the place-based Ex-Post Forecast

Utilising the Ex-Ante designation of each infrastructure element as a starting point, referring to Figure 2 and Tables 1 and 2 below, the vulnerabilities and network interdependencies of each infrastructure component were analysed against the increased stressors caused by climate change through the indicators, metrics and judgements outlined in Table 2. In this initial desktop testing of the framework, the case studies sites listed in Table 3 are explored at high level as demonstrated in Table 1, considering the effect of increased climate change stressors resulting from SSP2-4.5 (IPCC, 2023). This middle-of-the-road development pathway (2.7°C increase by 2100) is where socioeconomic factors broadly follow historical trends and CO₂ emissions stay at around current levels before declining in the second half of the century. The process of capturing context specific vulnerabilities, impacts and risks, generally followed the guidance of ISO 14091 (International Organization for Standardization, 2021) and the Climate Change Risk Assessment (CCRA) as outlined by The Physical Climate Risk Assessment Methodology (Coalition for Climate Resilient Investment, 2024).

Referring to table 1, the example that applies to test site 1, each of the 16 risks were assessed for applicability to each element of infrastructure at site and community scale with possible designations referencing the behavioural characteristics set out above, A – Robust, B – Ductile, C - Collapsing. Where the risk was determined not to be relevant the intersection of the table is marked with an 'x', i.e. sea level rise poses not site scale risk to an inland location of high elevation for example. Utilising the resources and data available from the

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sources described in the 'Latent Capacity Indicators / Responsible bodies' column on Table 2, an indication of what latent capacity is available to each element of infrastructure is given which assists in the selection of the ex-ante score. An indication of the interdependencies each element of infrastructure is then given - this is a high-level indication at this stage with further and more granular research into cross scale interdependencies required at each test site.

Moving towards an understanding of the point that threshold is exceeded for each infrastructure component, and how each components performance buffer may affect that of other elements or systems, the latent capacity of each component is investigated. This is done by ascertaining the standards to which the component was designed, constructed and is maintained, comparing those with the stresses that climate change will bring above and beyond the benchmark of 2021 by 2100 in the chosen IPCC scenario (Pörtner et.al., 2022). To assess the vulnerability to these effects, the current adaptive capacity of each element and system of infrastructure is evaluated in terms of collective (community, LA or government led) adaptations at a wider scale and autonomous (asset owner led) adaptations at a site scale (Buth et al., 2017). Evaluating adaptive capacity involves establishing technical and financial resource availability but must also consider factors such as awareness, social capital, and governance. To this end, the framework accounts for the impact of planned adaptations and those underway across scales as included in Table 2. An updated behavioural trajectory is then assigned to each infrastructure component based on the analysis of these variables.

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Figure 1: Establishing the Ex-Ante Benchmark

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Table 1: Example Desk Top High-Level Summary

EXAMPLE (TEST CASE 1) DESKTOP HIGH-LEVEL SUMMARY																								
	Risks 1-16																Latent Capacity information	Ex-Anti Benchmark	Interdependencies	Planned Adaptations	Threshold Exceedance	Ex-Post Forecast	Impact	
	1 – River and surface water flooding	2 – Subsidence, bridge scour, pipeline disturbance, slope and embankment failure	3 – Interruptions in power or heating fuel supply	4 – Disturbance of operations to sewage treatment	5 – Reduced mobility for goods and people	6 – Interruptions to broadband, TV, and communications	7 – Disruptions to social infrastructure and services delivery	8 – Damage to the built environment, plant, trees or building fabric	9 – Direct health and safety risks to people	10 – Disturbance to business operations	11 – Reductions to water supply and interruptions to service	12 – Crop failures	13 – Biodiversity loss	14 – Coastal flooding	15 – Wildfire	16 – Soil depletion	Complete, Partial, Limited, None	A – Robust, B – Ductile, C - Collapsing	D= Direct, I = indirect, x = none	Collective (Full, Partial, Limited, No information available)	Autonomous (Full, Partial, Limited, No information available)	Anticipated date of change of status by without further adaptation	Behaviour by 2100 based on SSP2-4.5 2.7°C increase	Minor, Limited, Moderate, Significant, Catastrophic
1 - PUBLIC WORKS																								
1.1 - Roads / Bridges / Paths	A	A	A	x	x	x	A	A	x	x	x	x	x	x	A	x	P	A	D	P	N	TBC	A	-
1.2- Flood defences	x	A	x	x	x	x	A	A	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	P	A	N	P	N	TBC	A	-	
1.3– Public Buildings	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	x	x	A	x	x	x	A	x	L	A	D	L	x	TBC	A	-
1.17 - Healthcare	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	x	A	A	A	x	x	A	x	L	A	D	P	x	TBC	A	-

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Table 2: Indicators and Adaptations

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	Ex-Ante Performance Indicators (or potential source)			Planned Adaptations				Latent Capacity Indicators / Responsible bodies			Indicator of future scenario (SSP2-4.5 2.7°C) increase by 2100	
	Site Specific	Community	County / City	National	Site Specific (Autonomous)	Community	County / City	National	Design Standards	Construction Standards	maintenance	Existing or potential indicators
1 – River and surface water flooding	Flood risk mapping for the insurance and financial industry (Geosmart, 2025). Floodmapper tool (FloodNav, 2025)	EA Flood Mapping (HM Government, 2025), Road closure information DfT.			Asset owner, advise from Property protection advisor (National Flood Forum, 2025), EA, LA, (insurance companies), economic viability IMD (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	EA, LA, Local Flood Risk Management Strategy. Flood RE. National Adaptation Programme.			Defra, EA, LA, BS EN Standards and CIRIA standards	EA, LA	Asset owner, PESA (HM Treasury, 2025)	Flood risk projections for the insurance and financial industry (Geosmart, 2025)
2 – Subsidence, bridge scour, pipeline disturbance, slope and embankment failure	Site specific investigations / CCRA.	Road closure data, supply interruption data, train delay statistics Highways Authority, Network Rail, OFWAT, OFCOM, OFGEM, GEMA			Risk assesment and maintenance programme	The UK Government Resilience Framework, National Adaptation Programme, National Highways Delivery Plan			HA, NR HSE	HA, NR HSE	Asset owner	PESA / Investment programme in assets / maintenance (HM Treasury, 2025)
3 – Interruptions in power or heating fuel supply	National Grid, UKPN, or SSEN outage data, DNO feed in registration, site specific investigations/CCRA .	National Grid, UKPN, or SSEN outage data, OFGEM, GEMA			Dependant on Socioeconomic circumstances, and specific site constraints	National Adaptation Programme. The Great Grid Upgrade. Adverse Weather and Health Plan. Project Union.			DNO, UKPN, SSEN	DNO, UKPN, SSEN	DNO, SSEN	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024). Future demand and supply analysis, potential for onsite generation
4 – Disturbance of operations to sewage treatment	Individual treatment works performance data, aggregated sewage discharge and spill data (FloodNav, 2025)	EA, OFWAT, HSE. flow and spill data (Southern Water, 2025). Treatment works performance data, aggregated			Septic tank? Reed beds/ NBS	Environmental Improvement Plan 2023, new 'Water Reform Bill'			EA, LA, OFWAT	EA, LABC	Water Companies, EA, OFWAT	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024). Water Companies KPI's / Fines

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		sewage discharge and spill data (FloodNav, 2025)						
5 – Reduced mobility for goods and people	PTAL rating, IMD and NAO data on access to transport (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	DfT, HA, NR, ORR, train operators, LA, UKHSA	Individual and Business continuity plans	The UK Government Resilience Framework, National Adaptation Programme	DfT, HA, NR, LA, BS Standards	DfT, HA, NR, LA,	DfT, HA, NR, LA, ORR	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024)
6 – Interruptions to broadband, TV, and communications	Regulators service data (OFCOM, 2025).	OFCOM (OFCOM, 2025)., Network & communications companies.	Individual and Business continuity plans	The UK Government Resilience Framework. Project Gigabit.	LA, OFCOM BS Standards / IEC Standards, NCSC	LABC, OFCOM	Asset owner	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024). Company investment programs, PESA (HM Treasury, 2025)
7 – Disruptions to social infrastructure and services delivery	IMD rating 2015 Barriers to housing & services (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	LA, UKHSA, NHS, Home Office, IMD rating 2015 Barriers to housing & services (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	Individual and Business continuity plans	Local Authority emergency plan, The UK Government Resilience Framework	LA, NHS, Home Office	LABC, HA, NHS, Home Office	LA, NHS, HA, Home Office	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024). Study of impacts from past disruptions. PESA (HM Treasury, 2025)
8 – Damage to the built environment, plant, trees or building fabric	Green Infrastructure mapping (Natural England, 2023)	LA, Insurance Companies	Individual and Business continuity plans	National Planning Policy Framework 2024, Local Plans, Building Regulations.	LA, Building regulations, HSE	LABC	Asset owner	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024)
9 – Direct health and safety risks to people	Health Data from IMD (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015; Ministry of Housing, 2019)	Local authorities, UKHSA, NHS, HSE, Emergency services	Asset owners (insurance companies)	National Planning Policy Framework 2024, Local Plans, Building Regulations.	LA, Building regulations, HSE	LABC	Asset owner	Met office Local Authority Climate Explorer (Met Office, 2024) PESA (HM Treasury, 2025)
10 – Disturbance to business operations	Asset owners, Tax returns	Local authorities, Insurance Companies, Local resilience forums, BEIS, GDP	Business continuity plans	The UK Government Resilience Framework.	LA	Asset owner	Asset owner	Bank of England/ PRA reporting (Prudential Regulation Authority, 2025)
11 – Reductions to water supply and interruptions to service	Market insight companies (MOSL, 2025) EA (Environment Agency, 2021).	Water companies, OFWAT, BGS, EA (Environment Agency, 2021).	Asset owners, economic ability IMD (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	The Drought Response Plan. Plan for Water. The Strategic Resource Options Programme. Adverse Weather and Health Plan	EA, Water companies	Water companies	Water companies	Met office (Met Office, 2024), Groundwater availability (British Geological Survey, 2019).

International Conference 2025: Towards Resilient and Sustainable Cities and Communities

12 – Crop failures	NFU statistics, Green infrastructure mapping (Natural England, 2023)	DEFRA	Asset owner, NFU	The UK Food Security Index and Plan. (Land Use Framework, under consultation)	DEFRA, EA	Asset owner	Asset owner	Met office (Met Office, 2024)
13 – Biodiversity loss	IMD rating 2015 Living Environment (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	Defra Magic Map (DEFRA, 2025)	Asset owner	EA, LA, EN, Environmental Improvement Plan 2023, (Land Use Framework, under consultation).	LA, EA, EN	Asset owner, LA, EA, EN	Asset owner	Adoption of Land use Framework, reporting by campaign groups, historical trends
14 – Coastal flooding	Flood risk mapping for the insurance and financial industry (Geosmart, 2025)	EA Flood Mapping (HM Government, 2025)	Asset owner, advise from Property protection advisor (National Flood Forum, 2025), EA, LA, (insurance companies), economic viability IMD (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	EA, LA, Local Flood Risk Management Strategy, A Plan for Change.	EA, LA	EA, LA	Asset owner	Flood risk mapping for the insurance and financial industry (Geosmart, 2025) and coastal risk screening tool (Climate Central, 2023) Met office (Met Office, 2024)
15– Wildfire	Historic records, 5 day look ahead granular risk forecast (Natural England, 2025)	Fire and Rescue Services, LA, FC, NE, local resilience forums. Risk forecast (Natural England, 2025), Low resolution mapping (European Forest Fire Information System, 2025),	Asset owners, economic viability IMD (Department for Communities and Local Government, 2015)	Wildfire framework for England, Forestry Commission England's National Emergency Plan	FC, Building Regulations, BS standards	FC, LA	FC/EA/LA	European Forest Fire Information System (European Forest Fire Information System, 2025), Met office (Met Office, 2024), Defra Magic Map (DEFRA, 2025)
16 – Soil depletion	Asset owners	Defra Magic Map (DEFRA, 2025)	Asset owner, EA, LA	Environmental Improvement Plan 2023	LA, EA	EA, LA	Asset owner	Met office (Met Office, 2024), Defra Magic Map (DEFRA, 2025)

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Table 3: Direct Hazard Exposure at Site and Community Scale

DIRECT HAZARD EXPOSURE AT SITE AND COMMUNITY SCALE: TEST CASES 1-10																								
	Climate Hazard					Scoping Review: Vulnerability to Potential Impact:											Low	✗						
	Sea Level Rise	Extreme Heat	Drought	Extreme Precipitation	More frequent and violent storms	1 – River and surface water flooding	2 – Subsidence, bridge scour, pipeline disturbance, slope and embankment failure	3 – Interruptions in power or heating fuel supply	4 – Disturbance of operations to sewage treatment	5 – Reduced mobility for goods and people	6 – Interruptions to broadband, TV, and communications	7 – Disruptions to social infrastructure and services delivery	8 – Damage to the built environment, plant, trees or building fabric	9 – Direct health and safety risks to people	10 – Disturbance to business operations	11 – Reductions to water supply and interruptions to service	12 – Crop failures	13 – Biodiversity loss	14 – Coastal Flooding	15 – Wildfire	16 – Soil depletion	Moderate	✓	Significant
Test Case 1		✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓				
With Phase 1 has been completed by a volume house builder, the development consists of homes varying in size from 1 bed to 4-bedroom houses. Regarding the socioeconomic characteristics of the area, the Deprivation Decile is rated as DD3.					Urban location close to major infrastructure, the site is in an area of low flood risk, high connectivity in terms of transport. The topography can be characterised as gently sloping, with permeable, seasonally waterlogged fine loamy over clayey and fine silty over clayey soils. The surrounding area is not heavily treed and does not link onto any forests or heathlands etc.																			
Test Case 2	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓				
A proposed as a net carbon zero development of up to 10,000 new homes. The project aims to create a vibrant town centre, educational facilities, and a network of green spaces, including play areas, allotments, and a town hall. DD7.					The development is planned for a peri-urban area. The area is outside of the national park and is typified by tree lined hedges, small copses between fields and gentle hills. The area has a low likelihood of flooding by rivers or the sea according to the EA. Climate central current trajectory by 2100 shows land within a 2 miles being below the annual flood level, despite being 8.7 miles inland.																			
Test Case 3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓				
A large brownfield site (potential 2,000 apartments). DD7, close to 3.					Climate Central current trajectory by 2100 shows land and road immediatel to the east of the site being below the annual flood level, but Government flood predictions until 2069 predict very low likelihood of flooding from the rivers or sea.																			
Test Case 4	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓				

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<p>A village that has grown significantly in the past 20 years or so with a population that has double since 2021. Effect on existing infrastructure and existing homes. DD7/8/5.</p>	<p>On the fringes of the South Downs national Park the parish is largely characterised by being relatively flat with the soil being chalky. Climate Central current trajectory by 2100 shows land close by being below the annual flood level but Government flood predictions until 2069 predict very low likelihood of flooding from the rivers or sea.</p>																			
<p>Test Case 5</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	
<p>Sea front development in the central area of the coastal town that faces socio-economic challenges – DD1.</p>	<p>The topography is characterised by a relatively flat low lying coastal plain and a shingle beach. The soil is primarily sandy and loamy, with some areas having clay or silty components.</p>																			
<p>Test Case 6</p>	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	
<p>2, 3, 4, and 5-bedroom homes, including a primary school and country park. New build in an urban area includes new green infrastructure. DD8/9, close to 3.</p>	<p>Sits on a low-lying coastal plain, the area is characterized by a high water table and serves as a catchment for runoff from the South Downs. Good cover of woodland and trees, including a high percentage of ancient woodland.</p>																			
<p>Test Case 7</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
<p>Small town hit hard by storm of 1987, 1910 great flood and others, subject to Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM). The focus here will be on existing homes exposure to extreme risks. DD5.</p>	<p>A vulnerable coastal area exposed to rising sea levels and increasingly frequent and violent storms.</p>																			
<p>Test Case 8</p>	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	
<p>Existing home in a rural, low connectivity, area within the SDNP, on flood plain of river. DD7</p>	<p>Village has a history of flooding. Flood warnings in January 2025, highlight the ongoing risk but the EA flood mapping suggests that the risk of flooding is low.</p>																			
<p>Test Case 9</p>	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	
<p>Peri-urban, in SDNP, close to town facilities (main line station etc.). Example of new build and older home. DD9/10.</p>	<p>The area is characterized by steep hills, open heathland commons toward the hill tops, extensive woodland through a mixture of ancient woodland and managed coppices, and pockets of remoteness. On Greensand, the soil is primarily acidic and poor and in places very shallow.</p>																			
<p>Test Case 10</p>	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	
<p>A new residential development offering a range of three and four-bedroom houses – over 1200 houses are planned with some of the early stages of the development now complete. The area is amongst the most deprived in West Sussex, DD1.</p>	<p>In a coastal town situated at the mouth of a tidal river with a shingle and sand beach. EA flood mapping describes the likelihood of flooding at Hampton park from rivers or the sea as very low. The Climate Central sea level rise screening tool shows that by 2100 significant areas could be below the predicted flood level.</p>																			

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Initial Findings

The UK is a high-income country, and West Sussex has the resources and infrastructure expected of a western democracy. The ex-ante benchmark utilised in this high-level study establishes that the infrastructure systems considered at the test sites operated and responded to interruptions in 2021 in a manner that facilitated full recovery with one exception – sewage treatment. However, this high-level benchmarking approach does not reveal the type, impact and extent of disruptions experienced at a more granular scale before systems rebounded to their previous state of functionality. Similarly, the latent capacity of each system and component across scales can not be established by a desk top analysis and will require a detailed study or the establishment of a reliable surrogate or direct indicator. Furthermore, the behavioural referencing system adopted does not allow for the temporal nature of disturbances thus either a more granular, performance scoring system based on a systematic codification of indicators that account for disruptions, is required, or each behavioural forecast needs to be qualified with the details of the impacts of disturbances for each site.

The process designed to establish the ex-post forecast has similar limitations at the desk top level, for example, the anticipated date of threshold exceedance is challenging due to lack of data apart from the case of new build developments that are then reliant on the existing processes of quality control in construction and future maintenance. However, the ex-post behavioural designations, given the plans and investment in place, are generally positive but do highlight some weak points particularly around how infrastructure systems respond to surface water flooding and storm damage, as both the magnitude and frequency of shocks are set to increase. Again, these positive findings relate to how systems and components are likely to recovery to their previous functioning and does not, at this level, identify the nuances of the extent and impact of disruptions prior to recovery. Similarly, more granularity regarding the risks of disruption to power, water and other utilities supplies, which was a common risk to all 10 test sites, along with the compound risks across systems that such failures will provide a greater insight into the varying resilience across the case studies.

Discussion

This study has revealed issues with the framework as it moves from theoretical to practical, particularly around the need to ascertain a measurement at both Ex-Ante and Ex-Post stage that encapsulate the period and extent of disruptions caused by extreme events at a local scale even when infrastructure systems fully recover. Infrastructure failures always impact at a local scale where stressors overwhelm latent resilience capacity, whereas some failures will have impacts at a regional scale and fewer will have national scale effects. For example, the risk of wildfire on the normal functioning of a road network is temporary and the road system will recover quickly but if a specific road is impassable at a time when people are evacuating a fire zone the localised impact can be catastrophic, and the output of the RAF needs to account for this.

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Resilience definitions and descriptions of infrastructure behaviours tend to accept temporary interruption to services whatever their consequences. A complimentary approach is that of disaster risk reduction, putting greater emphasis on the robustness of infrastructure systems and components to avoid disruptions - encouraging robustness against threats for continued use during extreme events in addition to understanding recovery after the fact. This approach needs to take account of the cost benefit ratio of a disturbance and preventative adaptation such as potentially higher design and construction standards. In turn, consideration of challenges around overcapitalisation is required, such as how much latent capacity will achieve total robustness, and if that is feasible or desirable, understanding that perfect can be the enemy of good.

There is a fundamental link between society's physical infrastructure and wellbeing, quality of life and prosperity (Dasgupta & Weale, 1992). The aim here is to work towards a RAF that avoids abstraction and provides place-based, context-specific insights that can inform adaptation planning that enables communities to thrive without leading to overcapitalisation or maladaptation. Given the known effects of climate change on the UK (Met Office, 2025) such a framework isn't simply a 'nice to have', it's a matter of national security (Cox K et al., 2020) (Wilson B, 2023)(Medland C, 2023). Preferably a full national publicly owned live digital twin of all infrastructure systems and components would be available and able to be tested against a variety of future climate scenarios and specific site-based shocks. In the absence of such a model more detailed data sets and indicators across scales are needed.

Economics is at the centre of resilience planning (Prudential Regulation Authority, 2025), and decision makers are tasked with balancing financial decisions around infrastructure with human and environmental needs. Prioritisation is required to establish what is critical, how important are certain aspects of quality of life compared to the ecological damage or financial cost in resolving them. This study highlights the issue of sewage (Petraikos K, 2025; The Rivers Trust, 2023), for example, but how much harm is done by the systems failure and what cost does that come at? The bigger question is what is society trying to achieve - resilience against what, by what, for who? This framework is not being developed as a tool to guide user priorities, but one developed to inform the decision-making process, whether that increases resilience to one system to the detriment of another or otherwise.

Conclusions

This paper in an initial response to the gap in the literature identified, setting out the issues around the creation of a RAF designed to evaluate infrastructure vulnerability holistically across scales from the perspective of place. Setting out to evaluate the overall architecture, and extensibility, of the draft framework, the study has identified areas where improvements are needed. Initial high level exploratory test case applications of the framework were undertaken to examine outcomes and the explore the repeatability and efficiency of the

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process. Moving from conceptual to practical, the insights gained from this testing are presented to the conference for discussion and will guide the future development and enhancements of the framework.

It is concluded here that:

- 1 – The behavioural forecasting examples utilised do not quantify disruptions sufficiently and are too remote from the temporal human experience of climate change shocks.
- 2 – More granular ex-ante and ex-post measures that account for the temporality, impact, and extent of disturbances are required.
- 3 – Detailed research to account for the impact of failures of dependant and interdependent infrastructure systems across scales at the test sites is required, potentially utilising a site-specific matrix describing level of dependencies and the impact of failures.
- 4 - The latent capacity of each system and component across scales cannot be established by a desk top analysis and will require detailed study.
- 5 - The anticipated date of threshold exceedance is challenging particularly regarding the test sites with older buildings due to lack of data regarding design and construction standards.
- 6 – To be a useful RAF that meets the challenge described above and produces meaningful outputs the lack of detail identified here needs to be rectified.

At the centre of this study is the impact of climate change on people where they live because resilience is not uniformly distributed - varying degrees of resilience co-exist within the same communities, from street to street, from house to house, infrastructure component to infrastructure component. Climate change is having a greater influence on the quality of life and livelihoods of people in specific places not only for location specific reasons but also due to vulnerabilities of interconnected infrastructure. A more localised perspective on infrastructure resilience will put people, rather than systems, at the centre of resilience discourse and this paper constitutes a small step forward in the development of a novel place-based holistic RAF that aims to do that.

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